

PRINCIPLES OF G2G, G2C MODELS IN E-GOVERNMENT

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Annotation: *The article compares the various theoretical analyzes of the G2G-State-to-State and G2C-to-Citizen models, which are among the key principles of the e-government system in the world experience, which is consistently applied in the process of e-government in the world today.*

Keywords: *e-government, E-governance, Government to Government, Government to Citizens.*

Introduction. The introduction of information and communication technologies in public administration will accelerate the development of the economy, reduce administrative costs, increase the efficiency and effectiveness of government agencies, meet the needs of the population for various information. expands opportunities for the formation of civil society, creates transparency in the activities of public services and reduces bureaucratic barriers.

New information and communication technologies can not only make a significant contribution to achieving good governance goals, but also make “e-governance” in e-government more efficient and consistent, and create other types of conveniences [1].

E-government is the application and slowdown of information technology in public administration to simplify and integrate work and processes, effectively manage data and information, strengthen public service delivery, as well as expand communication channels to attract people and expand their capabilities. possible. [2]. One of the characteristics of e-government is to provide citizens with a single access point for all public services [3].

The main goal of e-government is to facilitate citizens 'service and interaction with the government by providing open services to citizens and using websites, as well as reducing time and costs for operations [4] .. For example, performing certain operations such as obtaining a certificate, paying state duties and applying for benefits. E-governance, ie "e-governance" is the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) to improve governance at various levels of government and the public sector and beyond [5].

There are three main target groups that can be distinguished in e-government concepts: government, citizens, and businesses. While external strategic goals are understood as services provided to citizens and businesses and stakeholders, internal goals are aimed at the government itself [6]. In world practice, the e-government system is formed on the basis of the following basic technological principles:

- 1) G2G (Government to Government)
- 2) G2C (Government to Citizens)
- 3) G2F (Government to Foreigners)
- 4) G2B (Government to Business)

Government-to-Government (G2G) is the process of electronic communication between government agencies. The goal of a successful G2G model is to have the necessary resources to achieve the goal of providing better services, collaboration, and support to the population. Thus, G2G will improve and enhance the process of cooperation and mutual support between government agencies. Communication between government agencies, that is, the exchange of information, is a process of establishing a process related to the mechanisms of cooperation and collaboration [7]. An important goal of G2G development is to improve and ensure the continuity of intergovernmental organizational processes by simplifying cooperation and coordination between government agencies.

Four key factors of ICT can affect the relationship between government agencies:

- 1) creation of a centralized general database to strengthen the secure state Internet, cooperation and interaction between government agencies;
- 2) provision of online services;
- 3) application of more effective e-commerce in transaction activities between government agencies;
- 4) transparency of management;

The development of the G2G model depends on the organizational structure of government processes and human resource management. G2G involves interactions between these various government agencies, firms and agencies, which increases the efficiency of government agencies' operational processes. In G2G, government agencies share the same database using the Internet, work together.

G2C (Government to Citizens) is an activity organized by the government to facilitate the provision of services to citizens, online data. includes interactions [9] [10]. The main idea is to give citizens the opportunity to interact with the government from their homes.

G2C programs allow citizens to ask questions to government agencies and receive answers; payment of fees, payment of taxes (income, real estate), renewal of driver's licenses, payment of transport tickets, change of permanent residence. The G2C category includes all interactions that can be made electronically between the government and its citizens. Governments can also provide information on the Internet, provide training, help citizens find jobs, and more.

The goal of e-government (G2C) is to effectively and cost-effectively provide citizens with a variety of information and communication technology (ICT) services and to strengthen the relationship between government and citizens through technology.

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